

Visualizing River Wye Water Quality

The following is a map of orthophosphate levels in the river Wye catchment, see figure 1. In this map, concentrations of orthophosphates increase as the many feeder rivers collectively contribute to the river Wye. This is important because when examined in relation to figure 2 showing chicken farming operations, the cause of orthophosphate levels to be above 0.03mg/L, when health can be affected, is connected to chickens. Intensive Poultry Units (IPUs) are being closely monitored to assess their effects on the environment including water systems, explains CPRW (2019). The map displays the continuing damage of IPUs on the Wye catchment.

Rasters are one type of way to visualize spatial data. Zhu (2016) explains that rasters are a continuous grid of square cells which represent their space with a single data point. Zhu (2016) additionally discusses how the spatial resolution, or size of the cell, can limit smaller details from being shown in the map due to the singularity of raster data. On the other hand, vectors represent features, points might represent buildings, lines signify paths like roads, and polygons show area like a field or lake (Zhu 2016). Essentially; rasters divide space into a series of units called grid cells, which represent an area of the Earth's surface and contain a value, and vectors assume that geographic space is continuous rather than divided (Zhu 2016). Data attributes are a result of data collection, they categorise features through name and/or collected values associated with the feature (Zhu 2016). For example, the features could be sampling locations along a river catchment and the values would be the results of the data collection, like dissolved oxygen concentrations.

In the case of this map rasters were used to create the slope Digital Elevation Model (DEM), as well as altitude in the Digital Terrain Model (DTM). In both models, each grid cell is given a designated value to represent; degrees for slope, and meters for meters above sea level. Vector data was used to show the Water courses as connected lines, Wye and Lugg catchment areas through polygons, and sampling sites including those of the Lugg and Rowing Club as points. Data attributes are seen in the sampling sites as the orthophosphate values that were collected, as well as the date collected. They are also seen in the categorization of names of rivers of water courses.

Map design depended heavily on symbolization and colour. In raster data this is seen in the darker colours representing steeper slopes, in combination with brown higher altitudes to greener lower altitudes. Vector data saw the red outline of the Lugg catchment to contrast the

blue of the Wye catchment and water courses. The red of the catchment matches with the sampling site, with specialized sites shown as triangles, seen in the Rowing Club site as well. The remainder of sites are represented as circles and their colours show their attribute differences; black for an absence of unhealthy orthophosphates ($<0.03\text{mg/L}$), and light blue for the presence of unhealthy levels ($>0.03\text{mg/L}$).

Figure 1: Orthophosphate levels in the river Wye catchment.

Intensive Chicken Production Units: Herefordshire, Shropshire & Powys

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 Intensive Chicken Production Unit data prepared by Herefordshire CPRE, Shropshire CPRE, Shropshire WT and Brecon & Radnor CPRW from a) publicly available Planning Applications via relevant County Council Planning Portals, b) Environmental Permit data and c) Survey.

www.brecon-and-radnor-cprw.wales
www.shropshirewildlifetrust.org.uk
www.cpreherefordshire.org.uk
www.cpreshropshire.org.uk

Figure 2: Location of chicken farms operating within the Wye catchment. Source (CPRW 2019).

Reference List

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